

Fatty Acid Composition and Characteristics of *Cassia kleinii* Seed Oil

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Cassia kleinii, a plant occurring in central to south India, belongs to family, N.O. Leguminosae. The plants of genera *cassia*¹ generally possess considerable medicinal value. No work has been reported so far on fixed oil from its seeds. Phytochemical screening of forest seed oils is a subject of intensive research to explore new alternative sources for conventional oils. It was therefore considered worthwhile to isolate the fixed oil from the seeds of *C. kleinii* using glc technique.

The cleaned and dried seeds (2 kg) of *C. kleinii* were crushed and extracted exhaustively with light petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) in a soxhlet apparatus. Removal of the solvent furnished a yellowish oil with a faint odour, which was purified through animal charcoal and Fuller's earth. The oil was subjected to various qualitative tests, e.g. picric acid test² for epoxy group and Halphen test³ for cyclopropene moiety. The characteristics of purified oil, determined according to standard AOCS⁴ methods, are given in the Table 1. The oil was saponified with alcoholic potassium hydroxide and the unsaponifiable matter was separated. The mixed fatty acids were converted to their methyl esters⁵. Glc of the methyl esters was carried out on a CIC gas chromatograph equipped with flame ionisation detector using stainless steel column (3 mm × 2 m) packed with 25% DEGS on Chromosorb and using nitrogen as carrier gas. The injection port, columns and flame ionisation detector block were maintained at 250, 180 and 180°, respectively. The methyl esters were identified⁶ by co-glc with authentic samples. The fatty acid profile is given in Table 1.

The results gave no indication of conjugation or *trans*-unsaturation or any other functional groups in the oil. No epoxy function could be detected in it. The oil is of non-drying type and indicated its potential for edible use after due processing. However, the seeds can not be a good source of oil to be exploited economically.

TABLE I—CHARACTERISTICS AND FATTY ACID COMPOSITION OF THE OIL

Yield of oil (%)	4.8
Specific gravity (at 30°)	0.957
Refractive index (at 40°)	1.473
Moisture content (%)	2.8
Acid value	2.02
Saponification value	182
Unsaponifiable matter (%)	3.08
Iodine value (Wijs' method)	92.2
Fatty acids (%)	
Palmitic	21.016
Stearic	1.031
Oleic	28.505
Linoleic	46.210
Linolenic	1.923
Arachidic	1.313

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